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Deliverable D2.1 - Report on solid-state phase transition and transformation as a function of temperature

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Report on solid-state phase transition and transformation as a function of temperature

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1 Introduction

Refractory materials are key enablers of Energy Intensive Industries (EII) such as steel, glass, cement, gas, petrol productions and even the aerospace industry. This is due to their chemical, physical and mechanical properties, which enable these materials to operate effectively at high temperatures for long periods. Due to their use in these EII, increasing the operational lifetime of these refractory materials can impact the carbon footprint of multiple high emitters. Thus, investigation of the microstructure (which is related to the initial chemical composition and the thermodynamic stability of compounds) at high temperatures is one of the key topics to address for the scientific research in the field of refractory materials.

In the present document, different studies on various refractories are disclosed (Table 1). The investigated products are in the form of monolithics, or shaped products (classical bricks or moulds obtained through additive manufacturing). The vast majority are unshaped castables, due to their versatility and easy production. Although, all the refractories presented share roughly the same composition: aggregates, additives, and binders. The refractory aggregates generally made between 60 to 85 wt.% of the total mixture and have dimensions commonly ranging from 0.1 to several millimetres. The aggregates have the pivotal skeleton role in the finished refractory and can significantly affect its performance. For this reason, various aggregates compositions are studied: alumina (referring commonly to the mineralogical form of corundum or alpha-alumina, Al_2O_3), aluminosilicate (andalusite, Al_2SiO_5 , or mullite, $\text{Al}_{4+2x}\text{Si}_{2-2x}\text{O}_{10-x}$), fused silica (amorphous silica, SiO_2), alumina spinel (referring commonly to the magnesium aluminium oxide, MgAl_2O_4 , with crystal structure belonging to the spinel group), or magnesia (referring commonly to the mineralogical form of periclase or dead-burnt magnesia, MgO). Furthermore, the amount of refractory additive powders may vary from 5 to 30 wt. %. The roles of additive powders are several: filling the voids of aggregates, improve packing efficiency, impart flowable properties to the wet mixture, emphasize plastic behaviour, or target specific phase transformations. In this latter case, here presented is the impact of hydrogen atmosphere on in-situ formations of secondary alumina due to SiO_2 evaporation. In contrast, at high temperature impact on in-situ formation of alumina spinel due to solid-solid reaction between Al_2O_3 and MgO fines is observed. Finally, the refractory mixture contains a binder, or a system of binders, which may contain highly reactive powders with low particle sizes (commonly below 0.05 mm) accounting from between 5 to 15 wt. %. The binding system has the pivotal role of sustaining the integrity of the refractory by creating a network which embodies all the previous mentioned elements present in the mix. Accordingly, its phase transformations, high temperature stability, mechanical and chemical resistance are decisive for the refractory product. On this subject, the majority of refractory castables use a calcium aluminate cement (CAC) as the bonding agent. In fact, castables may be classified based on the amount of cement (in particular the amount of lime (CaO) present in the mix. CAC is a well-known product for its early strength and fast-hardening properties due to metastable calcium aluminate hydrate phases. However, at high temperatures these metastable phases transform causing a decrease in strength, sintering and expansion phenomena, and the development of internal stresses. Additionally, though CAC is the most common binder used for refractory castables, in recent years other bonding systems have been employed. For example, one bonding agent is comprised of nanometric particles of amorphous silica (SiO_2) in suspension, also called colloidal silica. Colloidal silica promotes the formation of siloxane bonds ($>\text{Si}-\text{O}-\text{Si}<$) giving rise to a dense network. Hence, the study of binder mechanisms, binder phase formation at high temperatures and the interaction between these developed phases and the other components in the mix (aggregates and additives) at high temperatures is crucial to guarantee the required properties. In this document, different characterization techniques are applied to recognize some of the effects of temperature or atmosphere on refractories.

Table 1 - List of the refractory products, acronyms, composition, investigated phenomena, characterization techniques, application and operational environment treated in the present document

Refractory product	Acronym used	Main composition	Sample preparation	Investigated phenomena	Characterization techniques*	Operational environment	Application
Alumina-silicate castables	NCC ZCC	Alumina-silicate Calcium Aluminate cement Colloidal Silica	Slurry mix casting	Phase transformations Sintering/expansion versus temperature	DSC TGA Dilatometry XRD	>1500 °C Directly in contact with liquid metal alloys	Investment casting moulds for turbine blades
Alumina-silicate castables	SL1 SL2	Alumina Alumina-silicate Calcium Aluminate cement	Casting	Post-mortem analysis Physical properties Phases transformations Microstructure evolution	PSD P&D XRD SEM-EDS	600-1200 °C Enclosed in between two other refractory linings for several months	Tundish safety lining for steel production
High alumina refractories	N/A	Alumina Alumina-silicate Phosphate-containing binder	Moulding and forming	Stability in hydrogen atmosphere Secondary phases formation	SEM-EDS	900 °C Hydrogen atmosphere	Direct Reducing Iron process
Fused-silica mold	IM1 IM2	Amorphous Silica Zircon	Injection moulding	Amorphous silica crystallization Microcracks formation Porosity network	XCT & SXCT SEM-EDS ML	1480-1600 °C Directly in contact with molten metal alloys	Investment casting of turbine blades for aircraft engines
Alumina-spinel castable	M-WFA M-TA	Magnesia Alumina spinel Alumina Magnesia Calcium Aluminate cement	Casting	Calcium aluminate phases formation at high temperature In-situ magnesia-alumina spinel formation	SEM XRD	1500-1600 °C Directly in contact with molten steel	Ladle working lining for steel making
Vanadium-containing Alumina castable	S71_5 CMA72_5 Sa2.5_S712.5 Sa2.5_CMA2.5 Sb2.5_S712.5 Sb2.5_CMA2.5 Sa_5 Sb_5	Alumina Calcium aluminate cement Calcium magnesium aluminate cement Vanadium pentoxide	Casting	Phase composition Dimensional stability Phase distribution Thermomechanical resistance	XRD SEM-EDS PLC CCS E&G moduli MoR RUL	650-900 °C Directly in contact with molten aluminium	Working lining for non-ferrous metallurgy
Basic monolithic	WL1 WL2	Magnesia Forsterite	Spraying	Post-mortem analysis Slag corrosion Steel infiltration	SEM-EDS	1500-1600 °C Directly in contact with molten steel	Tundish working lining for steel production

*DSC (differential scanning calorimetry), TGA (thermogravimetric analysis), XRD (X-ray diffraction), PSD (particles size distribution), P&D (porosity and density), SEM (scanning electron microscopy), EDS (energy dispersive scattering), ML (machine learning), PLC (permanent linear change), CCS (cold compressive strength), E&G moduli (elastic and shear moduli), MoR (modulus of rupture), RUL (refractoriness under load).

Table 2 - Refractory castable classification based on the lime share from the binder in the mix.

Name	Acronym	CaO content only from cement binder [wt.%]
Cement-containing Castable	CC	CaO > 2.5
Low-Cement Castable	LCC	1 < CaO < 2.5
Ultra-Low-Cement Castable	ULCC	0.2 < CaO < 1
No Cement Castable	NCC	0 < CaO < 0.2
Zero Cement Castable	ZCC	CaO = 0

2 Characterisation techniques employed

The techniques used in this document are briefly described below:

- Thermal analysis such as thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), can help in assessing the phases transformations associated to the chemistry of the system and their interaction, but also to assess the effect of the atmosphere on the refractory;
- Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) are microscopical and spectroscopical investigations which could allow to observe the microstructure of the material and, detect their composition and crystallinity;
- Dilatometry, porosity and density (P&D) and permanent linear change (PLC) are techniques to assess the physical properties and the stability of the refractory;
- Cold compressive strength (CCS), elastic moduli, and modulus of rupture (MoR), are mechanical characterization techniques used to identify the performance of the material subjected to stresses, high temperatures or severe thermal cycling;
- More advanced techniques, for example, X-ray computed tomography (XCT) and synchrotron X-ray computed tomography (SXCT), coupled with numerical techniques as machine learning, allow for 3D visualization and quantification of microstructural features. Such techniques give a more comprehensive understanding of the microstructure than two-dimensional imaging techniques (as for example SEM) and may be used to better evaluate the porosity.

3 Microstructural evolutions of refractories at high temperatures

Refractories are used in a wide range of applications, ranging from melting furnaces and boilers to chemical reactors, and their behaviour is intrinsically related to the environment to which they are exposed. The atmosphere, whether oxidizing or reducing, has a decisive influence on the stability, durability as well as the performance of refractories, and their behaviour under these conditions is matter of study. For simplicity, the majority of research on refractory materials has been carried out in oxidizing atmospheres. Industrial applications involve combustion or processes at high temperatures in oxygen-rich environments. In such atmospheres, refractories must maintain their structural integrity and resist thermal shock, surface erosion, and microstructural changes caused by extreme temperature variations. While refractories are relatively stable in oxidizing atmospheres, they are still subject to deterioration, especially when exposed to thermal fluctuations. Therefore, the ability to withstand these conditions is a key factor in the design and selection of refractory materials, and continued research in this area can lead to significant developments.

Research on refractories in oxidizing atmospheres has also aimed at enhancing the sustainability and performance of these materials. Notably, significant attention has been given to refractories with low cement content, which offer both environmental and technical advantages. Reducing the use of cement materials substantially reduces the carbon footprint of the refractory material, as cement is a major source of CO₂ emissions in the construction and refractory industry. Moreover, refractories with low cement content have an optimized microstructure that enhances their resistance to thermal shock, thereby minimizing the adverse effects of repetitive heating and cooling cycles.

Alternatively, incorporating recycled constituents, such as vanadium oxide recycled from slags, in manufacturing refractories represents an innovative approach to sustainability. Vanadium oxide, which is a by-product of certain refining processes, can be reintegrated into refractory manufacturing, promoting the circular economy and reducing dependence on virgin raw materials. Studies indicate that partial substitution of traditional cements with alternative components, such as vanadium oxide, not only helps reduce industrial waste, but also provides improvements in the chemical stability and erosion resistance of refractories. This approach underscores the importance of encouraging more sustainable practices in the refractory industry, seeking a balance between technical performance and environmental responsibility.

In the context of the industrial transition towards using hydrogen as an alternative to carbon, it is equally relevant to investigate the effect of hydrogen on refractories. Reducing iron ores using hydrogen is one of the most promising initiatives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in the steel industry. However, introducing hydrogen as a substitute for carbon poses new challenges for refractory materials, as they face operating conditions that have not been fully explored. In highly reducing environments where hydrogen replaces traditional fossil fuels, refractories could experience a significant alteration of their physical and chemical properties, directly affecting their performance.

In conclusion, this analysis reviews the main phenomena affecting refractory materials under different atmospheres, including the usual oxidizing conditions as well as reducing environments where hydrogen is used. The development of more sustainable refractories, such as those with low cement content and the use of recycled components such as vanadium oxide, represents a proactive response to the demands of sustainability and efficiency in modern industry. Furthermore, the study of the effect of hydrogen in refractories presents itself as a fundamental area for the industry's evolution, in a context where decarbonization and the adoption of clean technologies are increasingly sought after. A thorough understanding of the behaviour of refractory materials in different atmospheres will provide knowledge about the phenomena behind their performance.

3.1 Refractories under oxidizing conditions

3.1.1 Influence of zero cement matrix on alumina-silicate systems

Zero cement castables (ZCC) are ceramic castables that contain exactly 0 % cement where a no cement castable (NCC) can contain up to 0.5-1 % cement to aid in coagulation. NCC is used in applications where the ceramic should maintain high dimensional stability under load at temperatures where creep is the main mode of failure. One such example appears in the aerospace industry, where a constant drive to improve the sustainability of the turbine blades has led to more complex component design to improve their efficiency [1]. Figure 1 shows the investment casting process, which is a common method to create these turbine blades.

Figure 1 - Investment casting process according to American Casting Company, adapted from [2].

It works by dipping a wax mould of the turbine blade repeatedly into a ceramic slurry and coating it with a ceramic stucco, this creates a ceramic shell that forms the mould for the turbine blade [3]. The next steps are to burn out the wax, pour in the molten metal, cool down the metal and finally knock off the ceramic mould to reveal the finished component.

The ceramic used to create these investment casting moulds has a specific set of requirements stemming from the application conditions during the subsequent casting of the turbine blade. The ceramic should result in a strong enough green mould to withstand manipulation, it should be dimensionally stable during the heating of the mould, and it should be able to withstand the forces of the pouring and the constant pressure of molten metal at high temperatures (i.e. > 1500°C).

Normally an Ultra-Low Cement Castable (ULCC) or No Cement Castable (NCC) would be used to create this ceramic body [4]. These types of castable usually use a very small but non-zero amount of cement in the recipe. The cement is essential to both coagulate the ceramic slurry to form the ceramic shell and to provide the green strength necessary for manipulation until the mould is fired. For this specific case requirements in investment casting however, even a small amount of cement will result in too much deformation at casting temperatures. The system will therefore require a true zero cement castable, where cement free binders in the recipe will aid in coagulation and setting.

In an alumina-silicate system, the effects of cement can be replaced by the network forming ability of colloidal silica [5]. Colloidal silica is a liquid consisting of H₂O and 30 wt. % silica. The silica is dispersed due to a high pH of 9.8, creating static repulsive forces. At room temperature the colloidal silica can be destabilized by manipulating the pH, creating a coagulation effect [6]. The network forming ability of the colloidal silica then allows for the creation of siloxane bonds (>Si-O-Si<), providing a low green strength to the system [7]. During the first heating up to 1000 °C, more siloxane bonds are formed, further improving the strength of the material, rivalling that of cement containing ceramics.

The zero cement castable will outperform the cement containing ceramics when heating to temperatures over 1000 °C. The cement containing ceramics will form a liquid phase, resulting in

significant creep at temperatures over 1500 °C and deteriorating the strength. The zero cement castable will maintain its strength at these temperatures due to the absence of a liquid phase.

Figure 2 shows the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the NCC and ZCC samples. The DSC indicates points where extra energy is required to heat the sample, usually indicating phase transitions and the TGA indicates the mass the evolution of the mass during heating.

Figure 2 - Thermogravimetric analysis and Differential scanning calorimetry in argon at a heating rate of 20K/min of (a) an NCC ceramic and (b) a ZCC ceramic.

The NCC recipe in Figure 2a shows peaks at 250 °C and 680 °C in the DSC curve related to the dehydration of several calcium alumina compounds. These peaks also correlate to the weight loss observed in the TGA curve in the same graph, indicating a loss of chemically bound water [8]. Most significantly, at high temperature some peaks are observed that are linked to the formation of a liquid phase of alumina, silica and calcium [9]. The DSC curve for ZCC Figure 2b shows no such peaks, indicating the lack of liquid phase formation.

Figure 3 shows the dilatometry curves for both the NCC and ZCC curves, this relates the expansion of the sample to the temperature.

Figure 3 - Dilatometry comparing NCC and ZCC ceramics during heating at 20K/min.

The dilatometry results in Figure 3 show a significant expansion of both the NCC and ZCC ceramics past 1400 °C. This expansion is linked to mullite formation [10], indicating that the lack of liquid phase in ZCC does not hamper mullitization.

Figure 4 finally shows the XRD measurements of both sintered and green samples of the NCC and ZCC compositions. The peaks indicate the presence of certain phases, indicated by letters in the top graph. The height of the peaks can be related to the quantity of these phases.

Figure 4 - XRD results for green bodies and post sintered bodies for both NCC and ZCC samples.

The XRD results after sintering in Figure 4 show that the amount of mullite formation is not hampered by the lack of liquid phase at high temperatures. Both the NCC and ZCC compositions start with similar amounts of alumina and mullite, where the alumina peaks indicate a larger concentration of alumina compared to mullite. The results after sintering at 1500 °C for 30 minutes show a clear increase in mullite content, where both NCC and ZCC have a similar concentration of alumina and silica react to transform to mullite.

Finally, the effects of this liquid phase on the strength at investment casting conditions of 1500 °C and 5 MPa, can be observed by hot modulus of rupture (HMoR) and creep in bending. The HMoR tests resulted in a hot strength of the NCC composition of 2 MPa and the strength of the ZCC composition of 6 MPa. As for the creep parameters, the creep observed in the NCC composition is so high that it would not survive the initial loading at high temperature, while the ZCC exhibits creep deformation that conforms to the requirements of the investment casting shells.

The difference in high temperature strength and creep resistance of NCC versus ZCC is clearly demonstrated by the HMoR and creep under bending results. This is explained by the DSC curve, where liquid phase formation is observed in NCC and not in ZCC. The lack of liquid phase did not lower the amount of mullite formations, as shown by the dilatometry and X-ray diffraction patterns, thus more favourable thermomechanical properties for investment casting shells for turbine blades were created.

3.1.2 Calcium Aluminate cement matrix in the initial state compared to post-mortem

Refractory castables containing calcium aluminate cement as binder may also be used as safety lining for vessels employed in steel making. The safety lining is a thick refractory layer applied to the inner section of the molten metal carrier such as the tundish. Safety lining refractories are employed

to compensate mechanical stresses and guarantee safe operations during casting. These refractory materials, once installed in the tundish, stay in place for several months. Thus, to guarantee high stability during the long usage and design even more performant materials, it is crucial to understand how their microstructure and the related properties evolve during application. Post-mortem analysis is one of the approaches that can be employed to achieve this. The castables under investigation in this section are aluminosilicate low-cement castables (LCC), hereinafter named SL1 and SL2, both in the new and post-mortem form (Figure 5). The new materials were cast in the lab from the as-purchased powders. Mineralogical and chemical compositions are shown in Table 3.

Figure 5 - Aluminosilicate castable for tundish safety lining (SL1) in the a) as-new, and b) post-mortem state.

The post-mortem materials were taken from the steel plants after 763 and 638 heats for SL1 and SL2, respectively. To better understand the in-service behaviour of the castables, initially the particle size distribution (PSD) test has been performed on the new materials. Due to the presence of aggregates with dimensions up to 6 mm, two techniques have been used. Laser diffraction method for the powder fraction with dimension below 1 mm have been combined with columnar sieving for the coarser grains fraction.

In order to understand the particles distribution and the resulting packing modulus, two theoretical models have been compared. The Andreasen model is classically used for cementitious materials, it uses a continuum approach to develop the most effective particles distribution following the equation:

$$CPFT = \left(\frac{d}{D_M}\right)^q \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where *CPFT* corresponds to cumulative percent finer than, *d* is the considered particle's size, *D_M* the biggest particle's size, and *q* is the distribution modulus. The parameter *q* is used as a reference parameter to understand the resulting packing density, or porosity (being strictly linked) of a certain particles' distribution. To achieve dense packing, Andreasen proposed a value of *q* between 0.21 and 0.37 depending upon the requirement of workability, hydration and material composition [11].

Table 3 - Chemical composition and mineralogical phases of the new, lab cast, castables.

Material	Chemical composition [wt. %]*	Mineralogical phases*
SL1	70.1 - Al ₂ O ₃ 23.8 - SiO ₂ 2.4 - TiO ₂ 1.5 - CaO 1.0 - Fe ₂ O ₃	α-Al ₂ O ₃ , andalusite, mullite, anatase, lime, quartz
SL2	78.2 - Al ₂ O ₃ 14.2 - SiO ₂ 3.4 - Fe ₂ O ₃ 1.8 - CaO	α-Al ₂ O ₃ , mullite, hematite, lime, quartz

*Chemical composition and mineralogical phases, reported here, originate from the material data sheet provided by the refractory producer.

Additionally, the Dinger-Funk model has been considered as it has also been developed to account for the impact of fines on the packing, following the equation:

$$CPFT = \left(\frac{d - D_m}{D_M - D_m} \right)^q \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where D_m corresponds to the lowest particle's size. Furthermore, Dinger and Funk indicated the best packing corresponding to the distribution modulus value of 0.365. Moreover, considering the packing optimization of a wide particles' distribution by following such model a q variation between 0.2 and 0.365 will not affect the porosity significantly [12].

The particle distribution in the castables investigated here has been designed to range from a few millimetres to a few micrometres (Figure 6a). Additionally, the distributions are multimodal curves with an increased amount of fine particles, below 10 μm , for SL2 with respect to SL1. The multimodal design of the PSD curve is well known to indicate the improved packing density of the castables [13]. The addition of more or less fine particles and aggregates, on the other hand, can tailor the rheology of the system and the hydration.

Figure 6 - Particle size distribution obtained for safety lining refractory castable mixes:
a) experimental data represented as CPFT as well as amount,
b) experimental CPFT curves compared to calculated Andreassen and Dinger-Funk models.

The distribution moduli, q , of the theoretical models is a result of the interpolation from the experimental data for the two safety lining refractory castable mixes (Figure 6b). The resulting distribution moduli has been calculated as 0.12 and 0.17 for SL1 and SL2, respectively. These values are not close to the theoretical best distribution moduli for highest packing factor as proposed by Andreassen and Dinger and Funk [14]. The reasons behind such discrepancy of the real to the ideal best values for distribution moduli are various. For example, there is no need here to have high density castables, thus promoting water evaporation during the drying step reducing spalling probability. Furthermore, an increased porosity in the permanent lining contributes to reduce the effective heat

conduction, having a strong impact on the thermal efficiency of the overall tundish system [15]. Indeed, porosity and density measurements for the materials tested (SL1 and SL2) show values far from the ideal ones related to high packing of the different grains.

Table 4 - Physical properties of the LCC castables studied.

Material		Apparent density [g/cm ³]	Open porosity [%]	True density [g/cm ³]	
NEW	SL1	2.64	18.72	3.32	
	SL2	2.72	21.84	3.53	
POST-MORTEM	Hot Face	SL1	2.59	21.17	3.28
		SL2	2.69	21.26	3.50
	Cold Face	SL1	2.71	18.62	3.29
		SL2	2.76	19.93	3.63

Furthermore, the presence of organic fibres has been observed in the castable mixes. These are acting as open porosity enhancer agents. The addition of polymeric fibres reduces the required drying time making the schedule shorter and more effective due to the creation of preferential pathways for water to evaporate from the bulk. A difference in the physical properties of SL1 and SL2 in the new state is observed through comparison of the two materials in Table 4. The larger amount of fines in SL2 should give rise to higher packing. Conversely, the open porosity value recorded for SL2 is higher than that recorded for SL1. Thus, the organic fibres and the possible addition of additives may play an important role in the porosity formation [16]

Slight differences are observed in the physical properties of the castable materials when comparing the new and post-mortem states. A general decrease of apparent density coupled with an increase of open porosity from the new to post-mortem materials was expected. The reasons behind the expectations were the operative conditions and the lifetime of the material. The hot face of the safety lining may reach temperatures of up to 1200 °C, while the cold face reaches a maximum of 600 °C. The temperature distribution may justify the progressive opening of microcrack networks contributing to the formation of open porosity. Also, at the hot face of the safety lining a progressive loosening of material is expected due to the chemical interaction occurring at the interface with the working lining. Similarly, mechanical erosion can contribute to these phenomena, in particular during the deskulling process (turning the tundish up-side down, to allow working lining detachment). The formation of secondary phases, glassy phases, and the progressive densification are phenomena which can occur due to the long lifetime of the safety linings (tens of months). However, the physical properties results do not confirm what expected. It is worth noting that the position in the tundish of the post-mortem sample plays a key role. The specimens discussed here come from the side wall central region. Moreover, an increase in open porosity in the post-mortem samples, especially for the hot face of SL1, is observed. On the other hand, rather small physical properties variations are observed at the cold face of both materials compared with the new state. The cold face in the safety lining castable is the region where the temperature gradient over the casting operations is the lowest. Thus, a stability in terms of microstructure and related properties is expected. Comparing the different safety linings, a difference is evident in the apparent and true densities.

The higher density values shown in Table 4 may also originate from the raw materials used in the production of the two castables. For SL1, as can be observed from the X-ray diffraction patterns (Figure 7), the majority of crystallographic phases are corundum ($\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) and mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$), for both the new and post-mortem materials. The portion of quartz seems lower for the post-mortem material. This is probably due to its contribution in the formation of complex multicomponent phases such as

anorthite ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$) and titanite (CaTiSiO_5), and glassy phases. Peaks at 21.2° and 34.8° correspond to the krotite ($\text{CaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, CA) phase, which during usage, reacting with alumina (Al_2O_3), transforms into phases more stable above 1000°C [17]. In this case, the conversion occurs predominantly towards CA_2 (grossite, $\text{CaO}\cdot 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$), a more stable high-temperature phase, due to the temperature ranges to which the material is subjected [17]. Thus, the XRD shows a higher peak intensity for the post-mortem sample in this region. Furthermore, it is difficult to identify mullitization, which originates due to the presence of andalusite or kyanite (two low-temperature stable polymorphs of Al_2SiO_5) in the recipe of SL1 [18].

Figure 7 - X-ray diffraction patterns of the LCC SL1 refractory material studied in the new (purple) and post-mortem (black) states compared.

Concerning the SL2 material, morphology and spectroscopy investigations were performed on the new and post-mortem samples. Firstly, microstructural analysis was conducted through scanning electron microscopy (SEM). This was followed by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) to identify the chemical composition in the SL2 microstructure. No variations between the new material and the post-mortem cold face have been observed in terms of microstructure and its composition. For this reason, reported here are only the post-mortem cold face results. The coupled techniques detected the presence of metallic chrome (Figure 8).

Figure 8- Scanning electron microscopy image of SL2 post-mortem cold face magnified area of grain-matrix interface corresponding to the red square of the overall section (bottom right corner). At right the table corresponding to the energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) results for each number point in the figure.

The metal is most probably “encapsulated” in the aggregates, with the highest dimensions observed being >1mm, potentially coming from a secondary raw material source. The presence of the metallic chrome induces an increase in the overall density of the resulting castable refractory material. Furthermore, the post-mortem material shows an enhanced area of metal distribution in the hot face (Figure 9).

Figure 9 - Scanning electron microscopy image of SL2 post-mortem hot face with the brighter stripes on aggregate corresponding to the substitutional solid solutions of α -Al₂O₃ and α -Cr₂O₃. At right the table corresponding to the energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) results for each number point in the figure.

This phenomenon may be due to the in-service high temperatures, more precisely at the hot face, fostering the formation of substitutional solid solutions of α -Al₂O₃ and α -Cr₂O₃. In fact, the brighter lines observed in Figure 8 are showing the formation of the previously mentioned chemical species. It is possible that Al-Cr spinel is formed during casting under low oxygen partial pressure and high temperatures, although this has only been reported in the literature in favourable conditions [19]. In addition, the presence of a metallic component in the castable may induce controlled formation of internal stresses, especially at high temperatures, compensating for external stresses (ferrostatic pressure and descaling load mostly) [20]. To support the previously explained results, the energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) outcomes are reported in the side table of each SEM picture. The results clearly indicate that the brighter spots (points 1 in Figure 8 and 3 in Figure 9) are composed of more than 98 % of chrome with only few traces of oxygen. Furthermore, points 2, 3, and 4 in Figure 8 indicate the grains are predominantly of α -Al₂O₃ with some traces of titania (TiO₂) and zirconia (ZrO₂). The TiO₂ and ZrO₂ probably originate from use as reinforcing agents or impurities in the raw materials (for example bauxite) [16], [21]. In the fines (points 5 and 6 Figure 8), many impurities have been observed, apart from the calcium other alkaline elements were observed such as sodium (Na) and potassium (K). These may have been added to the recipe with the purpose of forming eutectic forming solid solutions at high temperatures with more stable phases such as silica (SiO₂) and Al₂O₃ to promote liquid phase formation. The objective of this would be to generate grain-matrix cohesion giving rise to higher strength [22]. In the hot face of the post-mortem sample (points 1, 2, and 3 Figure 9), the formation of solid solutions between α -Al₂O₃ and α -Cr₂O₃, as previously mentioned, is supported by the brighter lines consisting of different quantities of the constituting elements. Moreover, the thermal cycles to

which the hot face of the material is exposed tends to form the metal oxide and diffuse in the alumina grains giving rise to the stripe-like pattern observed. On the other hand, point 4 of Figure 9 shows the presence of alkaline elements and additional components such as SiO_2 . Finally, it was possible to understand several mechanisms ruled by the physical properties and correlate them with the material in the new and post-mortem state. It is important to note that the design of the product (such as, the particle range and their distribution, and the presence of additives such as organic fibres and metallic inclusions) has the most significant impact on the microstructural and chemical composition variations at high temperature. It is particularly interesting to understand the composition and the resulting microstructure in terms of crystalline phases, morphology and chemical composition for safety lining materials. Especially because the refractory materials used in the safety lining for the tundish, are not in direct contact with molten steel and/or slag which is the principal source of impurities in other cases. The interface with the other linings (working and insulation) did not induce any noteworthy interactions. Furthermore, a strong variation of physical properties and composition has been proved to occur during operations, not only comparing the new to the post-mortem materials but also considering the hot and cold faces. Finally, refractory design, operative thermal cycles, temperature distribution and the surrounding chemical environment may induce drastic changes in the composition of the refractory bulk state.

3.2 Analysis of materials under reducing atmosphere

Iron ore is crucial for producing iron, yet its processing typically involves blast furnaces, which are notorious for their high carbon emissions, contributing roughly 7 % of global greenhouse gases [23]. This environmental impact has pushed the iron and steel industry towards greener methods, including exploring hydrogen as a viable alternative for reducing iron minerals.

Hydrogen, though not new to iron production, is gaining renewed attention as a promising reducing agent and alternative fuel. Traditionally, hydrogen makes up about 10 % of the reducing atmosphere in blast furnaces. However, increasing this proportion poses safety challenges since these furnaces are not designed for higher hydrogen levels. Mid-20th-century innovations introduced alternative ore reduction processes that utilize gaseous atmospheres rather than solid carbon reductants to address this. Notable examples include the MIDREX and Energiron processes (Discussed in more detail in the CESAREF Deliverable 3.3), which rely on direct reduction using primarily natural gas. These methods allow for better control of emissions and have the potential for future reductions, particularly as the availability of hydrogen rises and reliance on natural gas diminishes. While this shift from carbon to hydrogen appears to be positive, concerns regarding how hydrogen can negatively affect the lifetime of refractory materials need to be considered. As hydrogen content increases, it not only accelerates ore reduction but may also influence the reactor's refractory components, which directly interact with the reducing atmosphere [24]. Such interactions could alter the microstructure of the materials, potentially affecting their mechanical properties.

Despite the renewed focus on hydrogen, its effects on refractories have been investigated for almost a century due to its strong reducing nature. Research dating back to the 1930s showed that hydrogen could reduce SiO_2 in refractory clays, providing early insights into which materials are most susceptible [25]. Other studies examined the visible effects of hydrogen, such as the darkening of materials after exposure, linked to the reduction of minor components like iron oxide and mullite, leading to oxygen deficiencies. For instance, a 1948 study, by Wright and colleagues, explored how reducing atmospheres impact mullite in refractory clay bricks, noting the formation of pseudomorphic alumina after hydrogen reduction [26]. Additional research has revealed that hydrogen can cause the formation of porous corundum due to mullite breakdown in both crystalline and glassy systems.

However, due to the complex composition and microstructure of refractories, many aspects remain only partially understood.

Refractories composed of alumina and silica undergo significant microstructural changes when exposed to hydrogen at high temperatures. Hydrogen can reduce silica (SiO_2), altering the structure based on the material's composition. In alumina-silica refractories, hydrogen's reduction of silica can lead to the formation of secondary phases due the reduction of compounds, increasing porosity and weakening the structure, especially in high SiO_2 content materials like bauxite [27], [28]. In contrast, corundum-based refractories show more resistance due to their lower silica content and denser structure, which minimizes reduction and degradation [29]. Additionally, the presence of binders like phosphates can influence the microstructure, particularly in hydrogen atmospheres, where phosphorus components might reduce, affecting the binding phase and the overall structural integrity [30]. These potential changes are critical to consider when selecting materials for use in hydrogen-rich environments, such as hydrogen metallurgy, where the choice of refractory can significantly affect the durability and performance of furnace linings.

Hydrogen can significantly alter refractory materials, particularly by reacting with and modifying key components, especially silicon-based ones. Aluminosilicates are among the most affected under hydrogen or carbon monoxide atmospheres and can be described by the following reactions at 900 °C-1400 °C [28], [31], [32]:

These reactions reduce the oxygen levels within the oxide phases of the refractories, leading to changes in their microstructure. This effect is illustrated in Figure 10 [33], where a material of phosphate-bonded alumina is exposed to hydrogen, showing the formation of secondary corundum. Additionally, there is a noticeable change in the morphology of mullite, as depicted in the Figure 10d, highlighting one of the effects of hydrogen exposure at 900 °C, a temperature similar to those used in iron reduction processes. This example demonstrates how hydrogen can indeed impact refractory materials.

Figure 10 - Microstructure of the studied refractory. a) not exposed to hydrogen, b) exposed for 16 h, c) exposed for 48 h, and d) sample from another region of the refractory exposed for 48 h.

Description of marks: The secondary corundum is highlighted in yellow, pore formation in blue and disintegrated mullite in d) is highlighted in red. M: indicate mullite+ glass phase and A: Alumina phase [33].

These findings underscore that hydrogen can significantly impact the microstructure of refractory materials. This makes it crucial to thoroughly investigate all potential consequences of hydrogen exposure, particularly regarding the loss of aggregate integrity and the morphological changes in phases like mullite. Additionally, hydrogen reduction can result in the formation of microcracks in these types of refractories.

Figure 11 - Microstructure of a refractory 90 % Al₂O₃, 9 % SiO₂, 0.2 % Fe₂O₃ a) refractory without exposure, b) regions of the material after exposure to 900°C for 96 h in red reduced regions, c) aggregate with reduced silica-rich regions and d) other regions of the material with visible changes.

Another case involves the aggregates of the refractory observed in Figure 11, where, despite a lower silicon content, certain regions undergo reduction, compromising the integrity of the material's aggregates.

Figure 12 - Refractory material 45 % Al₂O₃, 48 % SiO₂, and 1.0 % Fe₂O₃, in a) material without hydrogen exposure b) material after exposure to 900 °C for 96 h at 100 % hydrogen. Several changes are observed after exposure to hydrogen, such as the deformation of the mullite and the appearance of bright spots due to the reduction and accumulation of reduced metallic elements in the refractory.

Other changes include the formation of new compounds due to oxide reduction, which accumulate in the material's matrix, further affecting its microstructure under the reducing atmosphere, as shown in Figure 12. Moreover, depending on the thermodynamic conditions, other oxides present in the refractories, such as Figure 10 [33], may also be reduced, forming new compounds that further alter the material's microstructure, whether in the aggregates or the matrix. This change within the matrix is also evidenced in morphological changes in the mullite since, in Figure

12a, a needle structure was evident. After exposure, this needle structure was observed to be deformed.

To summarise, the increase in the usage of hydrogen is emerging as an element in the transformation of industrial production methods, particularly within the iron industry, where it serves both as a fuel and a reducing agent. Transitioning to a hydrogen-based system, however, presents significant challenges due to the unique behaviour associated with hydrogen-rich environments. Research has shown that these conditions lower oxygen activity, which in turn causes microstructural changes in refractories. In particular, the integrity of aggregates can be compromised as reduced elements like silicon alter the material's structure. Additionally, hydrogen's influence leads to the decomposition of compounds such as aluminosilicates (mullite), further contributing to these microstructural transformations. These findings point out that hydrogen affects the mechanical properties of refractories and plays an important role in changing their microstructure, a key factor for future industrial applications and research.

4 Microstructural evolutions of fused-silica systems at high temperatures

Fused silica is an amorphous variant of SiO_2 with great interest in high-temperature applications. As illustrated in Figure 13 [34], when compared to other materials commonly used in refractory applications, such as alumina and mullite, fused silica has the lowest thermal expansion over a large temperature range.

Figure 13 - Thermal expansion characteristics of several ceramics [32].

Such outstanding dimensional stability makes it an excellent candidate for refractories applied in the aerospace industry. These materials are known as ceramic cores, and they are tools employed in the investment casting of turbine blades. The cores create precise and complex cooling passages in turbines that are essential to improve the energy efficiency of aircraft engines [35]. In the investment casting, a ceramic core is placed inside a wax model. The model is then coated with a ceramic shell, forming a mould. Once the wax is melted away, molten metal is poured into the inlet of the shell, and the core remains in place, shaping the internal structure of the blade, as shown in Figure 14 [36], [37], [38]. After the metal casting is completed, the ceramic core must be carefully removed, leaving behind the cavities in the turbine without damaging the metal. Fused silica has the advantage of being easily dissolved in a caustic solution, unlike materials such as alumina that are more challenging to remove from cast [39], [40]. Fused silica has also a lower sintering temperature (1150-1250 °C) compared to alumina, which ranges between 1400 °C and 1500 °C, requiring an excessive energy consumption [41]. Therefore, due to its thermal stability and ease of removal post-casting, fused silica is one of the most used refractories in the investment casting of turbine blades for aircraft engines [42], [43].

Figure 14 - (a) Ceramic core inside a mould for the investment casting of turbine blades [34], (b) 3D model of a turbine blade, highlighting the cooling passageways created by the ceramic core [35], (c) aircraft engine produced by Safran, showcasing where the turbine blades are located [36].

However, the application of fused silica is limited because it cannot withstand the high casting temperatures required for new-generation superalloys, which range from approximately 1480 °C to 1600 °C [44]. At elevated temperatures, fused silica softens due to its low viscosity, leading to significant creep deformation. This softening results in defects, such as deviations from the desired shape and positioning tolerances of the cooling channels within turbine blades [45]. Besides that, at temperatures over 1550 °C, silica cores react with alloying elements like Al, C, Ti, and Hf, causing the formation of metal oxides and gas porosity, which further reduce the dimensional accuracy and surface quality of the components [46], [47], [48].

To address these challenges, the versatile nature of silica allows for improvements in high-temperature behaviour through adjustments in phase transformations and structural changes, such as crystallisation and porosity. The crystallisation of fused silica into cristobalite inhibits softening and creep deformation, which is essential for enhancing the high-temperature stability and mechanical properties of silica-based ceramic cores [49]. This occurs because cristobalite forms a barrier layer that hinders the viscous slip of fused silica [50]. Additionally, it counteracts the sintering shrinkage due to the volume expansion associated with devitrification [51], [52]. Crystallisation begins at around 1300 °C and increases rapidly between 1500 °C and 1600 °C, though the rate of transformation and temperature are influenced by factors such as particle size and shape [49], additives [50], [51], [53], impurities [54], [55], and sintering temperature [56]. Further studies are required to fully understand how to control these variables for improved properties. During cooling, between 300 °C and 200 °C, β -cristobalite transforms into α -cristobalite, resulting in a volume contraction of about 5 %, which produces microcracks on the surface of the silica particles, as shown in Figure 15 [51]. These microcracks can relieve thermal stresses in the solidifying metal and facilitate the dissolution of the core with a caustic solution [51], [57], [58]. However, excessive cracking can weaken the core, leading to ceramic failure during cooling. Therefore, the extent of transformation must be carefully adjusted to achieve an optimal balance [59].

Figure 15 - Microstructures with SEM/BSE of silica-based ceramic cores with zircon addition (a) as-received; (b) after heat treatment at 1525 °C, showcasing the microcracking due to the crystallisation of fused silica [49].

The microstructure of fused silica ceramics is typically analysed using SEM. While this technique is valuable, X-ray computed tomography (XCT) offers the advantage of visualising and quantifying microstructural features in three dimensions, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the fused silica behaviour at high temperatures [60], [61]. Several studies have employed XCT to evaluate the microstructure of fused silica, particularly regarding porosity. Silica-based ceramic cores must maintain approximately 30 % open porosity to ensure their removal after casting with a caustic solution, while also possessing sufficient strength to withstand mechanical and thermal stresses during metal solidification [62]. For example, Li et al. demonstrated the relationship between micropores and

creep resistance [63], while another study by Li et al. showed the evolution of closed pores into interconnected pores at higher sintering temperatures [64]. However, despite its potential to provide detailed insights into microstructural features and defects, XCT is primarily used for inspection and quality assurance at the macroscale [65], leaving its application for the microstructural analysis of ceramic cores largely unexplored.

Even less used is Synchrotron X-ray Computed Tomography (SXCT), which offers higher resolution compared to conventional XCT. This technique enables the quantification of features down to 1 μm at BAMline, the beamline at the light source used in this study, Bessy II [66]. Recent upgrades at the beamline now allow for in-situ and operando studies to be routinely performed. These upgrades have enabled the investigation of the microstructural evolution in ceramic cores under operational conditions such as high temperatures and mechanical stresses. This makes SXCT a powerful tool for analysing phenomena such as phase transformations, porosity changes, and microcrack formation in real time [67], [68]. However, in-situ experiments can be challenging due to sample movement and the thermal stability of the equipment [66]. Therefore, this report shows results involving ex-situ experiments on ceramic cores after sintering (1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and after casting (1530 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), with a focus on the changes occurring in the fused silica phase.

The microstructure of the three studied samples is depicted in Figure 16. Two of the samples were fabricated by Injection Moulding (IM1, IM2), a process where ceramic material is injected into metallic moulds to form precise shapes [69], while the other sample is fabricated by Additive Manufacturing (AM), also known as 3D printing, where the core is built layer by layer according to a digital model [70]. The matrix consists of fused silica with zircon additions, which appears brighter in the CT scan. The matrix consists of fused silica with zircon additions that appear brighter on the CT scans. These variations in shades of grey indicate differences in material composition, as each material attenuates X-rays differently [71].

Figure 16 - Cross-sections of SXCT images of silica-based ceramic cores after sintering: IM1, IM2, and AM.

After casting temperature, a microstructural change observed within the fused silica was the surge of microcracks, shown in Figure 17. As mentioned before, the microcracks are linked to the crystallisation of fused silica, one of the most important phase transformations of silica-based ceramic cores. Based on observations of the cross-section image volumes, the sample that presents most microcracking is IM1, followed by IM2 and last is the AM sample. Future quantification of these microcracks using SXCT with higher resolution is anticipated and could provide further insights into the devitrification of fused silica.

Figure 17 - Microcracking in fused silica grains of samples IM1, IM2, and AM

The IM2 sample presented some regions with melt fused silica grains associated to large pores, as shown in Figure 18. When reconstructed three-dimensionally, it appears that these regions are associated to the pore fibres that are present in the IM2 sample but not in IM1. This reaction of fused silica might account for the lower MOR at high temperatures presented by the IM2 sample. The melting of fused silica grains may also be associated with less cristobalite transformation observed via the microcracking of IM2 in comparison to IM1 and to the lower zircon content of this sample since zircon particles act as a pinning agent for fused silica grains [72].

Figure 18 - Larger pores present in the IM2 sample after cast temperature associated with fibre pores and MOR of IM1 and IM2 samples at high-temperature.

These results were an exploration of different microstructural features during high temperature treatment that were observed in different ceramic cores with SXCT and that have not previously been described in the literature. In the future, in-situ analyses and correlation of these observations with the processing and properties of ceramic cores will be conducted.

5 Microstructural evolutions of Alumina Spinel systems at high temperatures

Castables are a class of monolithic refractories composed of a mixture of refractory aggregates, bonding agents and additives. Among various castable types, the spinel containing systems (both pre-formed and in-situ) are widely used for ladle linings. This is due to their improved refractory properties such as chemical resistance, low carbon content, low thermal conductivity and their thermo-mechanical characteristics compared to refractories containing primarily alumina.

Spinel-based refractories have been developed for their ability to produce high-quality steels due to their low carbon content. Spinel-based refractories are applied mostly to steel ladle linings to help avoid carbon pickup, which influences the steel quality. While there are over 200 known spinels, those associated with refractories are mostly alumina-magnesia spinel, MgAl_2O_4 and picrochromite, MgCr_2O_4 [73]. MgCr_2O_4 -containing refractories are being slowly phased out, due to their carcinogenic nature when exposed to high temperatures and pressures, and are being replaced by MgAl_2O_4 [73]. For this report, the term spinel will refer to MgAl_2O_4 . Aside from aiding in the provision of high-quality steels, spinels over the decades have been found to have high refractoriness, high corrosion and slag penetration resistance and better thermal shock resistance [73].

5.1 Alumina-Spinel (pre-formed)

Most refractory aggregates naturally occur and are obtained through mining. This is not the case for spinels as there are no known natural sources yet. These synthetic aggregates are produced by fusion or sintering processes which makes them expensive compared to spinels formed in-situ. To minimize the volumetric expansion and cracking during service as observed in in-situ formation of spinel, preformed spinel has been used in steel ladles due to their dimensional stability even at high temperatures. Though alumina-spinel (preformed) castables have demonstrated excellent properties, there are still areas to improve such as their thermal shock and corrosion resistance.

The influence of two different alumina aggregates, Tabular Alumina (TA) and White Fused Alumina (WFA), on the microstructural evolution of alumina-spinel refractory castables (Tabular Alumina-spinel castable, M-TA, and White Fused Alumina-spinel castable, M-WFA) at high temperatures is discussed in this section. A microstructural study was carried out with SEM after sintering both castables at 1500 °C. Despite overall higher open porosities in WFA aggregates [74], the WFA aggregates look denser in the microstructure compared to TA aggregates as shown in Figure 19. This could be due to the easier diffusion of the matrix into the larger open pores of WFA at high temperatures. However, the matrix of M-TA castables appear denser with well distributed, tiny pores whereas M-WFA castables possessed larger pores in the matrix. SEM images show the presence of hibonite (CA_6) at the borders of the alumina aggregates for both M-TA and M-WFA castables.

Figure 19 - Microstructure of alumina-based spinel castables sintered at 1500 °C: A) M-TA and B) M-WFA.

However, CA_6 seems to be evenly distributed along the tabular alumina aggregates. In M-WFA castables, CA_6 tends to form on discrete parts on the surface of the aggregate but in denser layers than in M-TA castables.

Furthermore, XRD analysis revealed beta-alumina ($\beta-Al_2O_3$) and $CaO \cdot 2Al_2O_3$ (CA_2) phases in addition to corundum and spinel after firing the both M-TA and M-WFA castables at 1300 °C (see Figure 20).

Figure 20 - XRD patterns of alumina-spinel refractory castables fired at 1300 °C and 1500 °C: (A)M-TA and (B) M-WFA.

At 1500 °C, the CA_2 phase was no longer present in the M-TA and M-WFA castables. However, a new calcium aluminate phase in the form of $CaO \cdot 6Al_2O_3$ (CA_6) was found at 1500 °C in both the M-TA and M-WFA castables.

In further semi-quantitative analysis, corundum peaks were discovered to be higher for M-TA than M-WFA castables at 1300 °C and 1500 °C as indicated in Figure 21, Table 5 and Table 6.

Figure 21 - XRD analysis of alumina-spinel refractory castables showing the differences in peak intensities of corundum fired at A) 1300 °C and B) 1500 °C.

A decrease in corundum peak heights were observed when castables are fired at 1500 °C compared to 1300 °C for both castables. All other phases present seemed to retain or have similar peak heights regardless of the sintering temperatures.

Table 5 - A semi-quantitative analysis of the phases in wt. % after 1300 °C heat treatment.

Phase	Corundum	Spinel	β-Alumina	CA ₂	CA ₆
M-TA %	77.6	16.2	0.6	5.7	0
M-WFA %	73.5	19.2	1.4	5.8	0

Table 6 - A semi-quantitative analysis of the phases in wt. % after 1500 °C heat treatment.

Phase	Corundum	Spinel	β-Alumina	CA ₂	CA ₆
M-TA %	70.7	15.1	0.6	0	13.6
M-WFA %	64.5	18.9	0.6	0	16.1

5.2 Alumina Spinel (in-situ formation)

Spinel is formed by the reaction of magnesia and fine alumina added to the refractory castable at elevated temperatures [75]. To investigate the reactive sintering of alumina and magnesia at high temperatures, in-situ X-ray diffraction measurement was conducted on bulk sample using synchrotron radiation at European Synchrotron Radiation Facilities, ESRF (see Figure 22). The QMAX furnace was utilized to investigate the sintering behaviour of alumina and magnesia in order to develop improved spinel-based refractory ceramics of the interest of high-temperature applications in the steel industry. This furnace enables in-situ experiments at elevated temperatures of up to 2000 K [76]. High-temperature X-ray diffraction was performed on a bulk sample, which is a very small disc shaped specimen with a diameter of 10 mm and a thickness of 1 mm. The experiment utilized a fixed X-ray energy beam of 10 keV and a two-dimensional detector, characterized by its ability to capture two-dimensional images or data, with a pixel size of 130 microns positioned 390 mm away from the sample. The one-dimensional diffraction pattern shown in Figure 23 is recorded after heating the bulk sample at 1200 °C with heating rate 10 deg/min and keeping isothermal heat treatment at this temperature

for 9.6 hrs to achieve spinel crystallization during the reaction of alumina and magnesia.

Figure 23 displays the qualitative information of all α - Al_2O_3 , MgO, and spinel peak areas. It indicates that the peak areas of both α - Al_2O_3 and MgO decrease as the spinel peak area increases with the increase of isothermal heat treatment to 9.6 hours. For further quantitative analysis of reaction kinetics of in-situ reactive sintering of alumina and magnesia, detailed Rietveld analysis is required.

Figure 22 - High temperature X-ray device at BM02, ESRF.

Figure 23 - The crystallization of spinel phase achieved through isothermal heat treatment at 1200 °C for 9.6 hours, using Al₂O₃-MgO refractory ceramics (stoichiometric composition was chosen, 71.67 wt. % Al₂O₃ and 28.33 wt. % MgO).

6 Microstructural evolutions of Alumina systems including a vanadium bearing slag binder at high temperatures

Over the last few years, the demand for calcium aluminate cement (CAC) has increased steadily, with more than 1 million tons produced worldwide by 2022 [23]. As lime production is highly energy-intensive [77], efforts to reduce CO₂ emissions aim to minimize the use of calcium aluminate cement (CAC) in refractory castables. This is of particular interest due to the reliance on imported raw materials and increasing ecological concerns [78], [79]. With initiatives, such as the European Green Deal, pushing for European industries to embrace a greener, circular economy the refractories industry is searching for low carbon alternatives to lime. A potential alternative can be found in the by-products of steel production.

Producing one ton of steel in an integrated steel plant generates about half a ton of by-products, slags (90 % by mass), dusts and sludges [80], [81]. This slag has potential applications beyond disposal [82]. For specific applications requiring strengthening the steel, vanadium metal at very low levels (less than 1 wt.%) is added to hot metal in the converter [83] to form alumina-vanadium or ferro-vanadium alloys (for automotive, jet engines, and airframes) [84]. During these processes, fluxing agents such as lime or dolomite are added to react with impurities in the molten iron or steel, forming slag that floats on the melt [83]. Consequently, vanadium can react with the fluxing agents and be found in BOF slags with other compounds. The mineral properties of the slag will differ depending on the production process and deposits [85].

The composition of vanadium-bearing slag, rich in alumina, lime and magnesia, allows it to serve as an alternative material to calcium aluminate cement in refractory compositions [86]. The substitution of calcium aluminate cement for refractory applications with high-alumina slags is a well-known process [87]. CAC is well known product for its early strength and fast-hardening properties [88]. Indeed, CAC mineralogy presents reactive calcium aluminate phases, such as monocalcium aluminate (CA), the main phase and small amounts of calcium di-aluminate (CA₂) and mayenite (C₁₂A₇) [23]. When hydrated below 27 °C, metastable calcium aluminate hydrate phases are generated such as C₂AH₈, CAH₁₀ and AH₃. If the temperature exceeds 40 °C, C₃AH₁₀ and AH₃ are dominant [88], [89], making the hydration process extremely temperature-dependant. At high temperature curing steps, these metastable phases transform into stable C₃AH₆ which causes a decrease in the strength of CAC. Some secondary cementitious materials such as slag can be used to prevent this reduction in strength [90]. Either slag can be used as fine filler incorporated with commercial cement to increase strength of CAC, or it can be used as a hydraulic binder itself.

Studies on the possibility of using vanadium-bearing slag as a hydraulic binder in refractory castables applications remain few, particularly under varying operational conditions such as temperature fluctuations. While it can offer potential benefits, there are major challenges to overcome in maintaining the desired properties of refractories when incorporating vanadium slag. Its reactivity and capacity to form hydrates (C₃AH₆, C₂AH₈, CAH₁₀, and AH₃) are the main parameters that affect the feasibility of slag as cement [13], [91]. Due to the ecotoxicity of vanadium oxide in its pentavalent state (it is carcinogenic), careful handling is required and investigation into the mineralogical forms present in the slag must be conducted [92], [93].

The ability of vanadium-bearing slag to provide comparable hardening and setting properties to calcium aluminate cement (CAC) is a challenge that needs to be investigated prior to further research. Despite the promising attributes of vanadium-bearing slag, several challenges and knowledge gaps persist in the literature. One significant concern is the potential leaching of vanadium and other toxic

elements during high-temperature operations. This leaching could pose environmental risks and affect the long-term stability of the castable materials. Therefore, this section addresses the use of vanadium slag in high-alumina refractory castable formulations to obtain high-performance refractory castables. Two vanadium slags with variations in composition are employed in this work.

6.1 Starting materials

Table 7 presents the composition of two vanadium-bearing slags (sourced from Calderys and Spaeter, Germany) with a particle size of $\leq 63 \mu\text{m}$, derived from the ferro-vanadium (FeV) process. These slags are labelled as slag *a* and slag *b* for the study. Secar 71 and CMA72, both calcium aluminate cements, were used as reference binders, with their compositions also listed in Table 7. Additionally, reactive and tabular alumina were used in castable production.

Table 7 - Chemical composition of the raw materials.

Type	Composition (wt. %)					
	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	V ₂ O ₅	Fe ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂
Tabular Alumina	99.9	-	-	-	-	-
Reactive Alumina	99.8	0.04	-	-	0.03	0.07
Secar 71	68.6	30.1	0.31	-	0.13	0.32
CMA 72	68.3	9.40	21.4	-	0.21	0.32
Slag a	74.0	6.13	15.7	2.05	0.38	0.85
Slag b	68.47	25.43	2.86	0.73	0.23	1.34

6.2 Castables preparation

Refractory castable recipes with low cement content were prepared following the Andreasen model, and with a q-value of 0.25. To study the impact of compositional changes, 2.5 wt. % and 5 wt. % of cement were replaced with slag. Reference castables S71_5 and CMA_5 are produced using 5 wt. % of Secar 71 and CMA 72, respectively. Castables with slags *a* and *b* completely replacing the cement are designated as Sa_5 and Sb_5, respectively. Vanadium slag and cement were combined in half amounts to create four formulations: Sa2.5_S712.5, Sa2.5_CMA2.5, Sb2.5_S712.5, and Sb2.5_CMA2.5 as seen in Table 8.

Table 8 - Composition of ultra-low cement castables with substitution of cement by slags in wt. %.

Raw Material	Grain size (mm)	Sample code							
		S71_	CMA_5	Sa_5	Sb_5	Sa2.5_S712.5	Sa2.5_CMA2.	Sb2.5_S712.5	Sb2.5_CMA2.
Tabular Alumina	(1-3)	82.5							
	(0.5-1)								
	(0.2-0.6)								
	(0-0.3)								
	(0-0.045)								
Reactive Alumina	(<0.001)	12.5							
Secar 71	-	5	-	-	-	2.5	-	2.5	-
CMA 72	-	-	5	-	-	-	2.5	-	2.5
Slag A	-	-	-	5	-	2.5	2.5	-	-
Slag B	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	2.5	2.5
Water	-	5							
Deflocculant	-	0.1							

6.3 Slags characterizations

Using FactSage, predictions of the phases formed at high temperatures were made for the quaternary system $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CaO-V}_2\text{O}_5$, with a fixed amount of V_2O_5 based on the composition of each slag. An example phase diagram of this system, with 0.73 % of V_2O_5 , associated to slag *b* at 1500 °C, is presented in Figure 24. According to the phase diagram and the equilibrium results from FactSage summarized in Table 9, slag *b* at 1500 °C does not form any solid phases containing vanadium. Instead, it primarily forms calcium aluminate phases such as $\text{CaAl}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (CA_6), CaAl_4O_7 (CA_2), $\text{Ca}_2\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_{28}\text{O}_{46}$, CaO_2 and liquid a phase. In contrast, thermodynamic calculations for slag *a* at 1500 °C (see Table 3) indicate the presence of a vanadium-containing spinel phase, along with $\text{CaMg}_2\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{27}$, CaO_2 and Al_2O_3 . The formation of the V-spinel phase in slag *b* suggests that vanadium may be more easily detectable in this slag compared to slag *a* with SEM investigation. The distinct high-temperature phases formed in each slag suggest different mechanical properties or stability, which could have implications for their industrial applications.

Figure 24 - Calculated phase diagrams of the system $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CaO-V}_2\text{O}_5$ with 0.73 % V_2O_5 (Phase diagram, FToxid, FactPS, at 1500 °C, 1atm) showing the slag *b* composition

Table 9 - Thermodynamics calculations using FactSage (Equilib, FToxid, FactPS) of the phases present in slag and at 1500 °C in the quaternary system $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CaO-V}_2\text{O}_5$ with fixed amount of V_2O_5

Slag A – 2.05 % V_2O_5	Slag B – 0.73b % V_2O_5
$\text{CaMg}_2\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{27}$	$\text{CaAl}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$
CaO_2	CaAl_4O_7
Al_2O_3	$\text{Ca}_2\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_{28}\text{O}_{46}$
V-spinel	CaO_2
Slag-liquid	Slag-liquid

Table 10 outlines the primary phases present in slags and cements. The two calcium aluminate cements and the vanadium-bearing slags have different crystalline phases, with slag *a* dominated by the spinel phase (MgAl_2O_4) and slag *b* by Krotite ($\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$). Grossite ($\text{CaO}(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)_2$) is present in all binders, but hibonite ($\text{CaO}(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)_6$) is exclusive to slag *a*. Hibonite is a compound with low reactivity for hydration. Based on phases analysis, slag *b* would be more reactive and function better as a hydraulic binder due to its higher content of CA and CA_2 phases compared to slag *a*. In CMA72, spinel is a prominent phase, whereas it is absent in Secar 71. Further microstructural analysis is required because

vanadium oxide, which is present in small quantities, did not form detectable crystalline phases as identified by XRD.

Table 10 - Main phases of the slags and the commercial cements determined by XRD.

	Slag a	Slag b	Secar 71	CMA
Spinel	+++	++		+++
Hibonite	++			
Grossite	+	++	++	+
Krotite		+++	+++	++

Figure 25 shows the shrinkage curves of the slags. The temperature T_s , which indicates the point at which the area falls by 2 % from its initial value of 100 %, indicates the start of the sintering process. Sintering temperature for slag *b* was found to be 1470 °C, whereas slag *a* sintering temperature is not precisely found but the curve’s trend suggests being 1550 °C at the latest or higher. It was discovered that slag *a* expanded due to presence of a spinel phase while slag *b* did not exhibit any expansion.

Figure 25 - The shrinkage curves of the slags heated up to 1600 °C.

6.4 Microstructure examination

Sample Sa_5 in Figure 26 shows a grain within the matrix with 40 μm layers, containing a vanadium oxide phase at about 0.7 wt. %. The vanadium appears within a spinel phase, most probably $Mg_3V_2O_8$ and a calcium aluminate phase, most probably $Ca_3V_2O_8$, as confirmed by FactSage calculations. The substitution of cement with slag negatively impacted the microstructure after firing, leading to less embedded aggregates compared to reference samples without slag. This is due to the lower hydraulic phases present in the slags, which reduces its hydrate-forming ability with water and later poor bonding.

Figure 26 - SEM micrograph of the castable Sa_5 fired at 1500 °C for 6h.

The slag is homogeneously dispersed within the matrix. The formation of CA₆ during sintering creates bond linkages between matrix particles and aggregates. The alumina grain present in sample Sa2.5_S712.5 (Figure 27) is attacked by Secar71 cement, forming CA₆ phases and reinforcing the links between particles. Vanadium-containing particles, however, remain in the matrix without reacting with the alumina grain. In the microstructure, these vanadium particles are confined to the matrix and don't interact with aggregates or calcium aluminate cement. This suggests that either the only reactive portion of the vanadium-containing slag would not contain vanadium, or the vanadium-containing slag functions as a filler rather than a hydraulic cement. In samples with 5 wt. % slag and no cement, CA₆ phases still form, and the slag shows highly reactive CA and CA₂ phases in X-ray diffraction patterns (Table 10), supporting the hypothesis of its hydraulic nature.

Figure 27 - SEM micrograph of the castable Sa2.5_S712.5 fired at 1500 °C for 6h.

6.5 Mechanical response

Adding slag to the formulation significantly reduces compressive strength, with samples containing slag showing at minimum approximately 1/3 of strength compared to the reference with Secar71 cement as observed in Figure 28a. The presence of slag weakens the hydraulic bonding effect, leading to increased porosity and lower mechanical resistance after firing. RFDA measurements, in Figure 28b, reveal that slag reduces both elastic and shear modulus, though the effect is consistent regardless of the slag quantity. Interestingly, sample Sb2.5_CMA2.5, which combines slag *b* with CMA72, maintains similar elastic, shear, and flexural strengths (Figure 28c) to the reference samples, indicating effective sintering and strong hydraulic setting behaviour due to the higher presence of calcium aluminate phases in slag *b* compared to slag *a*. This suggests that the combination of slag *b* and CMA72 may be beneficial for preserving strength properties, whereas other combinations, especially with slag *a*, lead to more pronounced strength reductions.

Figure 28 - a) Cold-crushing strength of slag-based castables and the references; b) E and G modulus of the refractory samples; and c) Cold modulus of rupture of slag-based castables and the references.

Figure 29 shows the profile obtained for refractoriness under load (RUL) measurements of samples Sa_5 and Sb_5 tested under a 0.2 MPa load. It shows that Sa_5 experiences greater maximum deformation (1.31 %) compared to Sb_5 (1.17 %), indicating lower resistance to load at high temperatures for Sa_5. However, Sa_5 reaches this deformation at a higher temperature (1564 °C) than Sb_5 (1406 °C), suggesting superior thermal stability and refractoriness. While Sa_5 is better suited for high-temperature environments, its higher deformation may be a limitation in applications requiring minimal deformation. Conversely, Sb_5, with lower deformation but at a lower temperature, might be preferable where lower deformation is critical.

Figure 29 - Refractoriness under load of pre-fired samples at 1500 °C for 6h, Sa_5 and Sb_5 (under compressive load of 0.2 MPa).

To summarise, the comparative analysis of the two slags, slag *a* and slag *b*, in combination with different calcium aluminate cements reveals differences in phase composition, thermal behaviour and mechanical properties. Slag *a*, characterized by the presence of the spinel phase and hibonite, demonstrates higher temperature resistance but higher deformation under load, indicating superior thermal stability but lower mechanical strength. Conversely, slag *b*, dominated by the krotite phase and containing more reactive CA and CA₂ phases, shows lower deformation and enhanced hydraulic binding, leading to better mechanical properties when combined with CMA72, as evidenced by the preservation of strength properties. While slag *b* appears to act more effectively as a hydraulic binder, promoting strong bond linkages and maintaining mechanical integrity, the performance of slag *a* is compromised by its lower hydraulic reactivity and higher deformation at high temperatures. Therefore, slag *b* may be preferable in formulations where maintaining mechanical strength and minimizing deformation are required.

7 Microstructural evolutions of Dead-Burnt Magnesia systems at high temperatures

In this section, the materials investigated are working lining refractories for the tundish which is used in the steel continuous casting. The working lining is the refractory directly in contact with the molten metal. Due to its application the working lining has to guarantee the confinement of the molten bath and has the duty of ensure steel quality. Additionally, the microstructure's composition and morphology of the working lining should reduce steel infiltration and slag corrosion in order to allow the production of the needed steel grade. Moreover, the working lining is a disposable material (sometimes also referred to sacrificial lining) which, after a fixed period, is replaced. The lifetime of a tundish working lining can vary from a few to tens of hours. As a consequence, the application and removal of this material has to be versatile and straightforward. The properties desired for the working lining of the tundish are chemical and thermodynamic stability, mechanical resistance but easy loosening, high porosity for quick application but low permeability for controlled infiltration and corrosion. Improving these properties is a complex engineering research challenge. One strategy to achieve this is fundamental research coupled with post-mortem analysis of the composition, microstructure and high temperature properties.

Tundish working lining refractory materials have a common chemical composition. They are composed of between 70 and 80 % of dead-burnt magnesia (magnesium oxide, MgO). The presence

of additives and purity grade choices for the material mostly depends on the producer and the quality of steel in contact with such refractories. The remaining 15-25 % is commonly forsterite, a magnesium silicate mineral phase of the olivine solid solution with formula Mg_2SiO_4 . It is known for its high melting point, above 1700 °C, low conductivity values and good mechanical resistance [94]. The remaining refractory materials are hematite (Fe_2O_3), silica and additional components such as plasticizers and bentonitic clay ($Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2 \cdot 2H_2O$). The tundish working lining, being the sacrificial lining directly in contact with the molten steel, high purity refractory products, with a high concentration of MgO, are chosen. In fact, over the years the concept of the tundish has changed from a vessel to distribute the liquid steel in the molds to a metallurgical reactor influencing the quality of steel [95]. Therefore, the interest around the refractories used as sacrificial layer has increased recently. Further key properties of the working lining include good thermal efficiency and the capability of loosening of the solidified skull without damaging the safety lining. In the past, the common working lining refractories consisted of silica-based boards or bricks. With the advent of monolithic products, and the increased need for higher quality steel, a shift towards the use of basic unshaped refractories (with MgO as principal component) has been seen. Currently, the majority of working lining refractory mixes used in integrated steel plants consists of gunning, spray and hot/cold setting dry vibratable masses. It is possible to distinguish between two of the mostly used products: the slurry gunning and the trickle (sprinkle) mixes [96]. For the application, the mix is bonded with water in the percentage of 20-30 wt. %, pumped through a hose and sprayed with compressed air to cover the safety lining surface. The sprayed thickness is proportional to the expected casting time and ranges from 40 to 100 mm. These mixes are placed behind a steel mould (form) in the tundish and subsequently heated to about 200-250 °C for approximately 1 hour [95]. During casting, the hot side of the mix (directly in contact with molten steel and slag) is compacted by a viscous melt (Figure 30) [97]. Behind this area the structure of the mix has a decreasing sintered structure and the final region, in contact with the safety lining, should be loose enough to allow easy separation after the casting sequence during the desking step (turning up-side down the tundish to allow working lining detachment).

Figure 30 - Tundish working lining regions formation during operation, a) schematic illustration and b) post-mortem sample.

Independently to the type of mix used, based on the purpose of the refractory, specific properties are targeted. Thermal efficiency is necessary to prevent steel cooling and keep the desired viscosity for the specific steel grade. Such properties can be achieved through low thermal conductive composition, tailored packing and addition of porosity enhancing agents such as organic fibres. Porosity, packing efficiency and organic fibres have different objectives, such as creating the loose structure for thermal efficiency and easy removal after the casting sequence [98]. During the drying step the loose structure should, however, also guarantee stability (avoiding collapses or spalling) favouring a rapid water escape. During operation, the working lining has to resist corrosion, reduce steel contamination and limit steel infiltration. Therefore, in order to balance the opposite tasks of thermal efficiency and drying requiring high porosity and permeability; corrosion resistance

demanding thermodynamic stability and low contact surface. The design of the product may involve addition of low melting phases and impurities (containing for example alkaline elements as Ca and Na) coupled with high purity MgO fines. Such formulation may promote the formation of liquid phases with high MgO content, once steel and slag infiltrate the microstructure. The local dissolution increases the viscosity of the molten phases diminishing its activity according to the Noyes-Whitney equation:

$$dW/dt = DA(C_s - C)/L \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

Where dW/dt is the dissolution rate, D the dissolution coefficient, A the surface area, C_s and C the concentration of the solid in the solution and in the liquid bulk, respectively, and L the diffusion layer thickness. This local dissolution phenomenon can be observed in the post-mortem material through scanning electron microscopy (SEM, coupled with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS)),

Figure 31 and Table 11, respectively. Steel and slag infiltration in the hot face of the working lining generates various solid solutions mostly Mg-based but containing several impurities such as Na, K, and Ca, as mentioned previously.

Figure 31 - Working lining in the a) as-new state EDS picture of the microstructure with focus and bottom miniatures of the alkaline clusters with MgO fines and b) post-mortem hot face SEM picture with steel and slag infiltration and marked EDS areas.

These species probably originate from either the slag, to balance its viscosity and eutectics, or from the clusters observable in the new working lining

Figure 31a [99]. In these areas, it is possible to see fines of MgO encapsulated in grains containing alkaline elements (probably pyroxene phases such as augite, pigeonite, enstatite and diopside). The steel infiltration, observed in

Figure 31b, which is less of a concern during the casting step than the corrosion by the slag, may originate during the idle time before deskulling. During this idle time some molten steel remains in the tundish for several hours and the sample analysed has been selected close to the lining bottom.

Table 11 - EDS chemical composition of the marked areas in

Figure 31b.

Position	Elements							
	O	Al	Mg	Si	Na	Ca	Fe	K
1	34.7	28.3	17.2	11.4	3.6	2.4	1.8	0.3
2	35.4	8.4	23.2	-	0.7	0.8	31.3	-
3	24.7	8.3	27.6	2.3	2.1	1.3	35.7	-
4	3.6	0.2	-	0.4	-	0.2	95.4	-
5	41.7	6.1	40.4	3.6	1.8	2.6	0.4	-

In conclusion, the tundish is pivotal for the steel casting sequence to operate properly. The refractories that make up the working lining of the tundish need a fine balance of different properties to respond to the sometimes incompatible characteristics required. Such conflicting properties discussed here included the packing factor and the resulting porosity distribution, permeability, thermodynamic stability, strength for collapse avoidance and ease of deskulung. To balance the properties required, some of the mechanisms involved in corrosion (being one of the crucial parameters for refractory lifetime) have been discussed. These mechanisms were then correlated with the design of such materials from a microstructural and chemical point of view through SEM and EDS experimental analysis.

8 Conclusions

This report presents the microstructural evolution of various refractory systems exposed to high temperatures. The focus is on aluminosilicate systems, fused silica, alumina spinel, calcined magnesia and alumina in combinations with vanadium slag recycling. Within the framework of this project, the effect of temperature on the microstructure in different environments, including oxidizing and reducing atmospheres, on phase transformations, microstructure and mechanical properties of refractory materials have been studied. Methods used in order to identify morphological changes were thermal analysis, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and advanced techniques such as synchrotron X-ray computed tomography (SXCT) for 3D visualization of microstructures. The results indicate significant phase transformations, including the formation of

secondary phases and changes in mechanical properties due to high temperatures. The key findings from this report include:

- Refractory materials, such as aluminosilicate and fused silica systems, undergo significant microstructural transformations at high temperatures, including phase transitions and changes in porosity, which can affect their mechanical performance.
- Low-cement and no cement refractories show improved high-temperature strength compared to traditional cement-based refractories, contributing to more sustainable applications.
- The use of hydrogen as a reducing agent presents new challenges for refractory materials, as it can alter the microstructure and mechanical properties of aluminosilicates due to loss of materials integrity.
- Innovations in characterization methods, such as SXCT, allow for detailed analysis of microstructural features such as porosity is an interesting aspect to evaluate and notice in order to identify discontinuities in the materials.
- This report shows the need for further research into the microstructural evolution of refractories due to the complexity of phenomena that can develop in these materials.

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